

implementation, these can be mitigated through teacher training, effective planning, and integration into classroom practices. By focusing on relevance, engagement, and reflection, educators can create assessments that truly measure student growth and adaptability.

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BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA CHET TILIDAGI O'QISHNI TUSHUNISHGA O'YINLAR VA TADBIRLARNING TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya. Chet tillarini o'rganish hozirgi davrning eng muhim talablaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda. Ta'lim sohasida ham boshlang'ich sinflarda chet tilini o'rgatishga bo'lgan e'tibor juda yuqori darajada. Men maktabda dars beraman tasviriy san'at fani mening asosiy yo'nalishim hisoblanadi. Jahon tillari universitetida Ikkinchi mutahassislik asosida kechki ta'limda o'qiyman. Dars tahlili

bizning kasbimizda juda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Boshlang'ich sinflarda chet tillarini o'rganishga ko'nikmalar biroz qiyinchilik bilan kichadi. Chunki ular ko'proq o'yinqaroq va sho'x bo'lishadi. Ularga darsda ham o'yin ham dars o'tish juda muhim hisoblanadi. Dars jarayonida o'yinlarning ahamiyati boshlang'ich ta'lim o'quvchilarining chet tillarini o'rganishi uchun asosiy vositadir.

Kalit so'zlar. *O'quvchilar, Interaktiv metodlar, so'z boyligi, qiziqarli, didaktik o'yinlar, tadbirlar, ravon nutq, zavqli, axborot texnologiyalari, raqamli vositalar, muloqot, guruhlar, videodarslar, hikoya, sarlavha, muvaffaqiyat, boshlovchi, rag'bat.*

Kirish. Chet tilini o'rganishda o'qishni tushunish - yozma matnlarni tushunish, sharhlash va ularga javob berish qobiliyatini o'z ichiga olgan muhim mahoratdir. Boshlang'ich maktab o'quvchilari uchun bu ko'nikma ayniqsa muhimdir, chunki u tilni keyingi o'rganish va akademik muvaffaqiyat uchun asos yaratadi. O'qishni tushunishning kognitiv nazariyalari matnni dekodlash va tushunishda fon bilimlari, lug'at va sintaktik tushunishning rolini ta'kidlaydi. Chet tilini o'qitishda lug'atning cheklanganligi va notanish grammatik tuzilmalar tufayli o'qishni tushunish qiyinroq o'lishi mumkin. Biroq, samarali o'qitish strategiyalari talabalarga ushbu qiyinchiliklarni engishda sezilarli darajada yordam berishi mumkin.

O'qishni tushunishning kognitiv nazariyalari matnni dekodlash va tushunishda fon bilimlari, lug'at va sintaktik tushunishning rolini ta'kidlaydi. Chet tilini o'rganishda o'qishni tushunish, ayniqsa, boshlang'ich maktab o'quvchilari uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega, chunki u keyingi til o'rganish va akademik muvaffaqiyat uchun asos yaratadi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, til o'rgatishda o'yinlarni kiritish o'rganish natijalarini yaxshilaydi. Misol uchun, tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, til o'yinlari bilan shug'ullanadigan talabalar ko'proq an'anaviy, ma'ruzaga asoslangan ta'lim bilan shug'ullanadiganlarga qaraganda yuqori motivatsiyani, lug'at va grammatikani ko'proq saqlashni va o'qishni tushunishni yaxshilaydi. O'yinlar, ayniqsa, boshlang'ich maktab o'quvchilari uchun samarali, chunki ular amaliy, interaktiv va ijtimoiy o'rganish tajribasiga bo'lgan rivojlanish ehtiyojlariga mos

keladi. Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, o'yinlar va mashg'ulotlar til o'rganishda kuchli vosita bo'lib, til ko'nikmalarini mashq qilishning interaktiv va yoqimli usulini ta'minlaydi. Ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sir, faollik va faol o'rganishni rag'batlantirish orqali o'yinlar asosiy til tushunchalarini mustahkamlashga yordam beradi va tushunish va ravonlikni oshiradi. Chet tili darslarida o'yinlardan foydalanish nafaqat o'quvchilarni rag'batlantiradi, balki chuqurroq o'rganish va til ko'nikmalarini uzoq muddatda saqlab qolishga yordam beradi.

Xulosa. Hozirgi kunda boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarning ta'lim olishlari va darslarning qiziqarli o'tilishi juda muhim. Har bir darsga o'quvchi qiziqarli bir mashg'ulot sifatida qarasa ko'zlangan maqsadga erishish oson bo'ladi. Rasm chizish, turli musiqali raqslar, tez bajariladigan shartlar, lug'atlarning yodlash musobaqasini o'tkazish orqali boshlang'ich sinfni chet tillarini o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqishlari ortadi. Statistika ma'lumotlariga ko'ra boshlang'ich sinf yoshidagi bolalarning xotirasi, qabul qilishi kuchli bo'ladi. Shuni hisobga olgan holda chet tillarini o'qitish qancha qiziqarli o'tsa va yaxshi bilim berilsa, kelajakda chet tillarini qabul qilish oson bo'ladi. Tadbirlarni ham bolalar o'zini erkin tutishi, boshlovchilik qobiliyati, do'stona munosabatlar, hayajonni yengish, oratorlik qobiliyatini yuzaga chiqarish uchun hizmati katta. Har bir darsga ma'suliyat bilan, bolalarni yoshidan kelib chiqqan holda turli hil o'yinlar bilan qiziqarli dars o'tish faqatgina yosh avlod uchun darsga bo'lgan qiziqishni orttiradi.

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DIFFERENTIATING INSTRUCTION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSON PLANNING FOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS WITH DIVERSE NEEDS

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***Abstract.** This article discusses using differentiated instruction in foreign language lesson planning for high school students with diverse needs. It emphasizes tailoring content, processes, and outcomes to accommodate various abilities, learning styles, and interests. Key strategies include content differentiation with varied materials, process differentiation through flexible grouping and scaffolding, and product differentiation with diverse assessment options. The article also highlights the importance of cultural relevance, student engagement with authentic materials, and real-world scenarios.*

***Key words.** differentiated instruction, foreign language teaching, high school learners, diverse needs, lesson planning, content differentiation.*

Introduction. In today's diverse classrooms, high school learners have varied needs, abilities, and learning styles, making it crucial for educators to apply differentiated instruction in foreign language teaching. Differentiation involves adapting lessons to meet students' needs, ensuring all learners can engage with the curriculum and succeed. For language educators, this means considering students' linguistic backgrounds, learning paces, and interests while addressing challenges like motivation and cognitive abilities.

Another critical component is process differentiation, which involves tailoring